

Empowerment of Women's Creativity at Dians Songket and Endek Housein the Village of Gelgel, Klungkung: A Perspective of Presidential Instruction

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ABSTRACT: This study focuses on empowering the creativity of the women of the Songket and Endek House Dians based on the perspective of Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000. The formulation of the problem is as follows: (1) Why does the empowerment of the Songket and Endek House Dians women's creativity still exist? (2) What are the implications for improving the quality of life of the population, especially women, in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000? The research method is qualitative in nature supported by bibliographical data sources to sharpen the conceptual, theoretical, and analytical framework. Gender analysis is used as an alternative tool to integrate the aspirations, interests, and roles of the population, especially women who are gender responsive. The findings show that the empowerment of Dians Rumah Songket and Endek has continued to exist through the pandemic period. This is inseparable from internal factors, namely the role of business actors, and external, namely the role of development actors (government, community, BUMN). In accordance with the business vision of Dians Rumah Songket and Endek, which is to develop businesses with positive aims to improve the quality of life of residents, especially women and realize gender equality. This has directly supported the targets that must be achieved in accordance with those set out in the MDGs guidelines, including alleviating poverty and promoting gender equality.

KEYWORDS: Creativity, Development, Empowerment, Gender Equality, Movement.

1. INTRODUCTION

As an integration effort aimed at improving the quality of life of the population, especially women in development, in the 1970s a feminist movement emerged to fight for the status of women through the concept of *Woman in Development* (WID), namely a special program to empower women in development. Woman in Development (WID) is a global program of thought originating from liberal feminism. Most international organizations such as the United Nations, the World Bank, and almost all Third World governments and even most NGOs in Indonesia also adhere to this idea (Fakih, 1996 and 1999). After a decade, the program with the WID approach was deemed a failure because the program and its implementation were specifically for women (Hubeis, 2010: 158)). Then came the concept of *Woman and Development* (WAD) from the neo-Marxist feminist movement. Even this WAD concept is still considered inadequate about changes in the fate of poor women (Mosse, 2002). Poor women are characterized as follows: having no financial assets, low income, lack of formal education, lack of consideration for their contribution, humiliated and vulnerable to extortion, violence, and oppression (Krisnawaty, 1993: 159). Then came the concept of *Gender and Development* (GAD) which put more emphasis on empowering poor women and gender justice. The concept of GAD offers a new perspective on alternative development and liberation of women from oppression and gender injustice (Mosse, 2002). The practice of the approach originating from the women's movement in Southern countries is also followed by almost all Third World governments, including Indonesia. The GAD approach where men participate in fighting for women's interests. Within the macro framework, the role of the state greatly influences the placement of women's positions (Handayani and Sugiarti, 2002:42)

Realizing the need to uphold justice in improving the quality of life of the population, especially women, in 2000 the Government of Indonesia issued Presidential Instruction No. 9 of 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming (PUG) in all fields of development. This Presidential Instruction was then instructed to all government officials, including Governors, Regents, Mayors to implement Gender Mainstreaming in order to implement gender responsive policies, programs, and implementation of development (Hubeis, 2010). This study focuses on empowering women's creativity in the Songket and Endek House Dians in Gelgel Village, Klungkung based on a gender and development perspective in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 of 2000 which is gender responsive.

Quantitatively, Presidential Decree No. 9 year 2000 has undergone many changes related to development policies and strategies that are based on a harmonious partnership orientation between men and women having equal rights, obligations, roles, and opportunities based on mutual respect, respect and participate in filling various fields of development. However, quantitative changes have not completely changed the position of women in filling development qualitatively. For this reason, policy programs and strategies for sustainable development are urgently needed so that discriminatory practices against women can be anticipated, including in the world of micro, small and medium enterprises.

This study focuses on empowering women's creativity at the Dians Rumah Songket and Endek based on Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 which is gender responsive. Dians Rumah Songket and Endek are companies engaged in the textile sector with Balinese woven fabric products including woven fabrics. Dians Rumah Songket and Endek have a positive vision for the surrounding community through preserving cultural heritage from generation to generation. This company was founded in 1997 in Pegatepan Hamlet, Gelgel Village, Klungkung. Based on historical records, Gelgel has been known since the royal era in Bali as the center of arts and culture, including the development of Balinese endek weaving which has been passed down from generation to generation. Dians Rumah Songket and Endek was started by a Balinese woman, Mrs. Ketut Agustini, who is also said to have been inspired by the elders in her husband's family. It was from there that he gained knowledge about the ins and outs of endek weaving and Balinese songket heritage which had been developed since the time of the Gelgel kingdom in Bali. Thanks to persistence with the support of husbands continued with their sons. This weaving business continues to grow in line with the development of tourism in Bali which has become one of the mainstays and tourist attractions for local, archipelago and foreign tourists. Until now, we have been able to get through the pandemic. Songket and Endek House Dians still exist.

Based on this background and thoughts, the discussion of the problems in this study includes: (1) Why does the empowerment of women's creativity at the Songket and Endek House Dians continue to exist? (2) What are the implications for improving the quality of life of the population, especially women in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000? By instructing the Presidential Instruction to all officials, including Governors, Regents, Mayors to implement Gender Mainstreaming (PUG) in all fields of development that are gender responsive.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study on empowering women's creativity at Dians Rumah Songket and Endek in Gelgel Klungkung Village from the perspective of Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000, was carried out through research, namely scientific activities aimed at obtaining data. In carrying out this activity it must be carried out in a systematic, rational, and valid way in accordance with the phenomena in the field. So that the credibility of research results can be accounted for. In this study used qualitative methods in which researchers assisted by other people as a means of collecting data in accordance with what will be studied. Data analysis was carried out both during and after the research was carried out. The research results are in the form of descriptions and interpretations. Gender analysis is used as a social structure analysis tool based on the assumption that both men and women work and participate in development according to their respective potentials, needs and interests and get benefits fairly.

3. DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Internal factors

The empowerment of women's creativity at Dians Rumah Songket and endek continued to exist through the vandemi period because internally the ideas and struggles of business actors emerged to develop and preserve traditional Balinese weaving businesses that have cultural values inherited from generation to generation. Endek and weaving craft business has been known since the 8th century, namely during the Balinese kingdom centered in Gelgel. At first endek weaving was only worn by the nobility and to be worn during ceremonies at temples. However, now the Balinese endek has been worn by various groups, including for school uniforms, employee uniforms, and has even become a tourist attraction. This internal development has encouraged several Balinese people to pursue endek and songket weaving, which were inherited from their predecessors. For example, Dians Rumah Songket and Endek was originally started by a Balinese woman, Ms. Ketut Agustini, by gaining knowledge from her husband's relatives. From a home industry business, it then developed into a weaving business which is well-known for being able to open job opportunities for the surrounding population, especially women who really need job opportunities to meet economic needs through side jobs that are not binding, but still need responsibility in accordance with the agreement of the perpetrators. business at Dians

Rumah Songket and Endek. The actors at Dians Rumah Songket and Endek have a vision related to empowering the creativity of the population, especially women, namely from the beginning it has been aimed at opening job opportunities and developing this business which has a positive impact, both in supporting the preservation of songket and endek weaving culture from generation to generation and wanting to help and increase the income of its workers according to their potential, needs and interests.

The Balinese are known to have traits that emphasize balance. These characteristics are reflected in the teachings of *Tri Hita Karana*, including the balance between material and spiritual, the balance between humans and God, the balance between humans and humans or society, and humans and their natural environment. Many religious values are embedded in the teachings of Hinduism, including the importance of cultivating mutual respect, having a sense of caring, being tall and honest. It seems that all these values have been passed down from generation to generation and are reflected in the business people at the Songket and Endek Home Offices. With these characteristics and characteristics, it became one of the foundations for the Dians Rumah Songket and Endek businesses to continue to exist through the vandemi period. One of the important factors that must be owned by humans both individually and collectively to realize gender equality is by forming individuals who are concerned or aware of gender so that awareness to uphold justice in improving the quality of life of the population, especially women can be realized in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 which is gender responsive.

Bali is known as a tourist destination since the Dutch Colonial period. Bali's cultural politics often causes Balinese culture to start to wake up again and has a positive impact on the development of cultural tourism until now. With that fact, tourism will exist and develop in tourist destinations if the culture with its various elements, including the Balinese songket and endek crafts, if Balinese culture is still alive in Balinese society. Therefore, the Balinese people should consciously preserve the cultural elements that have been passed down from generation to generation and are able to produce creativity and aesthetics that have a positive impact on the survival of the supporting community. Dians Rumah Songket and Endek whose existence is in tourist destinations seeks to develop and perpetuate the business of songket and endek weaving as a cultural heritage and as a tourist attraction. For a tourist destination to have an attractiveness, there are at least 3 conditions that must be met, including: (1) There is something to see (2) There is something to do (something to do) and (3) There is something that can be bought (something to buy). These three conditions are elements to publicize tourism (Karyono, 1997).

3.2. External Factors

Empowering the creativity of Dians Songket and Endek in improving the quality of life of the population, especially women, can develop and exist through the vandemic period. In addition to internal factors, externally the role and support of development actors (government and other related parties) cannot be ignored. Since 2000 the Indonesian government issued Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in all fields of development. This Presidential Instruction is instructed to all government officials including Governors, Regents and Mayors to program, plan and implement development that is gender responsive. To empower the creativity of the Songket and Endek House Dians, the Regional Government of Klungkung Regency and Bali Province such as the Human Resources (HR) Service, BKKBN, and other government agencies, conducted visits, evaluations, coaching, cooperative relations with several BUMNs.

The obligation of the regional government, in this case the local government of Klungkung Regency, is to plan, organize, maintain, and supervise and support textile industry business activities that are positive and gender responsive in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000. So far, the attention and support of the local government. Relevant agencies, such as the Bali Provincial BKKBN and the Human Resources Service for the local government of Klungkung Regency, official visits from government officials and establishing cooperative relationships with BUMN in the Klungkung Regency environment. In increasing the creativity of weaving workers, coaching is also held through the activities of related government agencies. To increase the knowledge and skills of weaving workers, business actors work together and receive support from the local government to assist in the form of facilitators, training, and so on. Therefore, the Dians Rumah Songket and Endek businesses strive to provide superior service, both in producing their products so that they become a tourist attraction as well as aiming to improve the quality of life of the population, especially women in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 which is gender responsive.

3.3. Implications for Improving Women's Quality of Life

The existence of Indonesian women today shows encouraging changes and developments. This is the result of the struggle and movement of feminism through a long historical process. Included in the business world, especially micro, small, and medium

enterprises which are of great interest to women. The business of Dians Rumah Songket and Endek was also started by a Balinese woman. This is done not only to support household life, but also to develop their own talents and creativity as well as work opportunities for residents, especially women, to fulfill their basic needs according to their potential and get benefits fairly. With increasing women's income through micro-enterprises, at least women's knowledge and opportunities to negotiate in the household increase. Their opinion begins to be considered when making decisions in the household. However, various reports, journals and research results of micro-enterprises initiated and developed by women face challenges or obstacles. For example, in terms of funding. The efforts made by the Dians Rumah Songket and Endek business actors are to get support from the owner of access in terms of being a male business actor (husband) as well as support, trust from the local and provincial governments and other institutions such as BUMN

The empowerment of women's creativity at the Songket and Endek House Dians based on the perspective of Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 has implications for several things, such as creating improvements in the quality of life of residents, especially women. Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 is one of the strategies offered by the Indonesian government to support and facilitate the formation of business organizations such as Dians Rumah Songket and Endek which also have a positive vision. This business was originally started by a Balinese woman. This business became famous, because it has been able to develop and preserve the weaving business which has been passed down from generation to generation and still exists today. In line with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000, the Songket and Endek Home Office has been able to open job opportunities for residents, especially women who are a certain social layer group with the characteristics of having no financial assets and lack of formal education.

From several research report data, it is shown that women with these characteristics are constantly looking for work opportunities to fulfill basic (subsistence) needs. The number of female workers in the informal sector is much higher than that of men, such as in the Department of Songket and Endek Houses. From the results of the report on the empowerment of women's creativity, Dians Rumah Songket and Endek from the start had a vision of creating a business that had a positive impact on the population, especially women. To realize this vision, internally these business actors already have the basics, such as traits and characteristics that emphasize balance, have high concern, provide justice to their workers according to their respective potentials, needs and needs and benefit in an economic way. fair, provide workplaces that comply with health standards, provide guidance to increase knowledge of creativity, provide a sense of security and comfort, etc.

In accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming (PUG) in all fields of development. The business actors of Dians Rumah Songket and Endek are not only trying to meet the basic needs of their workers, but are also working to improve the quality of their workers. In this case the Dians Rumah Songket and Endek business actors have the principle that their workers also have a big share in determining the success of the Dians Rumah Songket and Endek business. Because of this, business actors try to create conditions that make their workers feel at home and enjoy working and participating in the Dians Rumah Songket and Endek businesses.

3.4. Promoting Gender Equality

In improving the quality of life and the basic needs of its workers, as well as in carrying out development goals, namely eradicating poverty and hunger and promoting gender equality, the role of business actors Dians Rumah Songket and Endek cannot be ignored, as well as the role and support of the relevant government parties. Gender Mainstreaming (PUG) as a just and equitable development strategy is increasingly being recognized as a development need and commitment. Gender Mainstreaming has demonstrated a strong commitment. The local government of Klungkung Regency and the Bali Provincial Office (HR, BKKBN) have conducted periodic evaluations, made visits, participated in promotions, conducted coaching, provided awards, and so on. From business actors Dians Rumh Songket and Endek are also trying to support the government's commitment in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000. This Presidential Instruction is one of the Indonesian government's responses to the commitment contained in the *Millennium Development Goals* (MDGs), namely efforts to fulfill basic human rights human beings through the joint commitment of UN member states to implement development goals. The MDGs are guidelines that contain targets that must be achieved, including gender equality, empowering women by improving the quality of life of the population, especially women, including those in the workforce (Hubeis, 2010).

The results of the research report on the empowerment of women's creativity Dians Rumah Songket and Endek from the start had a positive vision. These business actors make plans, programs and implementation based on the assumption that workers

who take advantage of job opportunities at the Songket Home Office also have a very large share in determining the success of the businesses they manage (as a reference to Pramono 1991). Therefore, for the business to continue to exist, it is necessary to create justice and equity based on the assumption that they or the workers in the Dian Rumah Soangkat and Endek weaving business are considered business partners who must be respected. They also need attention, guidance, adequate workplaces that meet health standards, and receive benefits according to their respective potentials, needs and interests.

Gender equality is of course not enough if it is only announced as a political discourse (Susanti, 2000). Equality is not by giving equal treatment to every human being who has different needs and abilities (Megawangi, 1999). To realize gender equality in accordance with the targets that must be achieved based on the MDGs guidelines and Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000, attention, support through programs, planning and implementation that are gender responsive, empowering women's creativity Dians Rumah Songket and Endek is carried out in synergy between actors' business with the government, related institutions, and business partners.

4. CONCLUSION

Upholding justice in improving the quality of life of the population, especially women, gender equality based on the assumption that men and women work and participate in all fields of development according to their respective potentials, needs and interests and benefit fairly. This is in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000. Empowering women's creativity in the Songket and Endek Home Offices, which from the start had a positive vision in preserving the art of weaving culture, improving the quality of the population, especially women, so that they work together and participate in the development of the tourism economy. As a tourist destination village, it also contributes to the development of the tourism economy. In general, Balinese people have traits and characteristics that include respecting the values of the balance of life contained in the teachings of Tri Hita Karana and the concept of *Ardhenareswari*, which in essence contains the value of caring between fellow human beings, men, and women. Men and women have equal status even though they are naturally different (Bandem, 2000). The nature and character internally are very influential on the existence of Dians Songket and Endek Houses. Internal factors that influence this business continue to exist, also supported by external factors, including attention and support from relevant government agencies in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 which is gender responsive.

Empowering the creativity of the population, especially women, has implications for improving the quality of life of the population, especially women. Business actors have a vision to develop businesses based on the assumption that both men and women work and participate according to their potential, needs, and needs and get benefits fairly. As a Tourist Destination Village (DTW). Dians Rumah Songket and Endek have contributed to the development of the tourism economy. There is awareness to uphold justice in improving the quality of life of the population, especially women, so in 2000 the Government of Indonesia issued Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in all fields of development and has been instructed to all officials including Governors, Regents, and Mayors to carry out sustainable development. gender responsive. Empowering the creativity of the Songket and Endek House Dians also supports Presidential Instruction No. 9 year 2000 in realizing gender equality, especially in the field of tourism economic development.

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